

Behavioral and Technological Advances of Stock Investment Decision: Insight from Indonesia's Banking Industry

Muhammad Ulil Albab¹, Yuni Nustini²

^{1,2}Department of Accounting, Faculty of Business and Economics, Islamic University of Indonesia

KEYWORDS: Financial Literacy, Risk Perception, Return Perception, Technological Advance, Investment Decision

Corresponding Author:

Muhammad Ulil Albab

Publication Date: 18 February-2026

DOI: [10.55677/GJEFR/04-2026-Vol03E2](https://doi.org/10.55677/GJEFR/04-2026-Vol03E2)

License:

This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license:

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the influence of financial literacy, risk perception, return perception, and technological advancement on investment decisions in banking sector stocks. A quantitative approach was used through a questionnaire survey of 130 investors aged 17–34 who have invested in banking stocks. Data were processed using multiple linear regression. The results show that financial literacy and technological advancement have a positive and significant effect on investment decisions, while risk perception and return perception have no significant effect. These findings emphasize the importance of financial literacy and digital investment platforms in driving investment decisions in banking sector stocks.

Cite the Article: Albab, M.U., Nustini, Y. (2026). Behavioral and Technological Advances of Stock Investment Decision: Insight from Indonesia's Banking Industry. *Global Journal of Economic and Finance Research*, 3(2), 116–125. <https://doi.org/10.55677/GJEFR/04-2026-Vol03E2>

INTRODUCTION

Amid the era of globalization, Indonesia's economic development has seen a significant increase in economic aspects. These aspects include economic growth, inflation, international trade, and investment in financial markets. Globalization drives increased market volatility, global index fluctuations, investment awareness, policy reforms, sustainable market trends, as well as innovation and technology, thereby creating various opportunities for individuals to invest while also contributing to job creation and poverty reduction. Investment has become important as it serves as a means of diversifying income and preparing for the future with the hope of increasing wealth value without causing significant losses.

Data from the (KSEI Indonesia Central Securities Depository, 2024) shows that the value of investments in financial instruments such as the capital market, mutual funds, stocks, and other securities has experienced significant growth from 2021 to September 2024. The value of funds recorded in the capital market increased from around Rp7,489 trillion in 2021 to approximately Rp13,946 trillion in September 2024, while mutual funds grew from about Rp6,840 trillion to roughly Rp13,153 trillion over the same period. In addition to the growth in fund value, the number of investors in the capital market has also risen at a consistent rate; at the end of 2023, the number of investors increased by approximately 18.01%, and grew by another 2.09% up to September 2024, with the capital market still being the most popular investment instrument compared to mutual funds and government securities. This description indicates that the capital market, especially stocks, has become the primary choice for investment activities among Indonesians in recent years. The capital market itself functions as a venue where demand and supply for long-term financial instruments meet, as well as enabling companies to obtain funding from the public (Sholeha, 2024).

In the capital market, banking sector stocks are considered one of the most attractive instruments for investors because this sector plays a crucial role in Indonesia's economy, including acting as an intermediary institution and provider of various financial services for both individuals and companies. Within the sectoral structure of Indonesia's stock market, the banking sector holds a very dominant position. Otoritas Jasa Keuangan, (2024) reported that the market capitalization of the banking sector's stocks reached around Rp3.9 trillion, or approximately 31.14% of the total sectoral stock index capitalization, making it the largest contributing sector on the exchange. In addition, the transaction value of banking stocks was also recorded as very high, at around Rp4,339 billion during the reporting period, indicating strong interest and trading activity in this sector compared to other sectors. The combination of a large capitalization share, high liquidity, and the perception of stability as well as long-term growth potential makes banking sector stocks a primary choice for investors in the capital market.

However, the dynamics of government policy show that investing in banking stocks still carries risks that investors need to consider. The issuance of Presidential Regulation Number 47 of 2024 concerning the Elimination of Bad Debts for MSMEs certainly had an impact on the correction of share prices of HIMBARA banks such as BBRI, BMRI, BBNI, and BBTN, each of which experienced a decline after the policy was announced. This situation indicates that investment decisions in the banking sector are highly sensitive to regulatory changes and market sentiment.

On the other hand, the growing public interest in investing is not always accompanied by adequate understanding of financial management and the risks involved. Many beginner investors tend to follow market trends without conducting thorough fundamental analysis, indicating that wider access to financial products is not yet fully balanced by good financial literacy. In this context, various behavioral and informational variables are suspected to play an important role in shaping investment decisions, particularly in banking sector stocks.

Financial literacy, for example, describes the extent to which individuals understand and are able to use financial information in financial and investment decision-making. According to Otoritas Jasa Keuangan, (2024) financial literacy includes knowledge, skills, and confidence that influence attitudes and behaviors in financial management to achieve well-being. Financial literacy can also be defined as an individual's ability to understand and use financial information in making effective investment decisions, so individuals with higher financial literacy tend to be more rational and cautious in making their investment choices (Usman et al., 2024).

In addition, risk perception also plays a role when individuals make investment decisions in stocks. Risk perception is the process of how investor view, assess, and interpret the risks of an investment instrument in relation to investment decisions (Putri & Ishanah, 2020). According to Kling et al., (2023), risk perception reflects a person's ability to understand the potential and impact of risky situations on the decisions and actions they take. Previous research has shown that the risk perception held by investors can influence investment decisions; when individuals do not understand or are not aware of the risks they will face, it can lead to dissatisfaction and negative experiences in investing (Arning et al., 2024; Li & Paudel, 2024).

Another important factor is the perception of return, which is defined as the assumption or expectation that prospective investors have regarding the expected rate of return from an investment (Junaidi, 2019). Perception of return includes expectations of various forms of profit such as dividends, capital gains, or bonus shares that may be obtained from owning stocks (Pratama et al., 2022). Previous studies have shown that the greater the perceived return, the higher the investor's interest in investing, although this relationship is not always consistent across different research contexts.

Technological advancement has also changed the patterns and methods of investors in investing, including in the banking sector stocks. Digital technology, such as investment apps, online stock trading platforms, and social media, has facilitated information access, accelerated transaction processes, and provided various educational resources related to investing (Ainiyah & Indrarini, 2022). Previous research indicates that technological advancements significantly influence investment interest and decisions by providing convenience, comfort, and a sense of security for investors when conducting transactions in the capital market (Nurfadilah et al., 2022; Pramono, 2023; Subowo, 2022).

This research is a development of the study conducted by Subowo, (2022), which examined the influence of financial literacy, technological advancement, perception of return, and risk perception on investment interest in the capital market in general. Although using a similar combination of variables, the study had not specifically distinguished the stock sector as the investment target and only measured interest levels, not actual decision-making behavior of investors. Based on these limitations, this study focuses on investment decisions, with banking sector stocks as the main object due to their dominant and strategic role in the Indonesian capital market structure. Thus, this study aims to re-examine the influence of financial literacy, risk perception, return perception, and technological advances in a more specific context, namely investment decisions in banking sector stocks.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

Theory of Planned Behavior

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) was developed by Icek Ajzen in the late 1980s as an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action formulated by Fishbein and Ajzen. Theory of Planned Behavior states that behavior is primarily determined by behavioral intention, which in turn is influenced by three components: attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). Attitude reflects an individual's evaluation of performing the behavior, subjective norms capture perceived social pressure from important others, and perceived behavioral control represents the perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behavior.

In the context of finance and investment, Theory of Planned Behavior is used to explain how beliefs about expected outcomes, social influence, and perceived control shape investment intentions and actual investment decisions. Financial literacy and perceived returns can be linked to beliefs about the consequences of investing (attitudes), while perceived risk and technological advances are related to perceived control over investment creation and management. This perspective helps clarify why investors with the same access to information can form different intentions and ultimately make different investment choices.

Investment Decision

Investment decisions refer to individual choices to allocate funds to specific financial assets with the aim of obtaining future returns (Amaliyah & Herwiyanti, 2020). In the context of capital markets, investment decisions involve evaluating alternative instruments such as stocks, bonds, and mutual funds by considering expected returns, associated risks, and the investor's time horizon (Putri & Ishanah, 2020). Previous studies show that these decisions are not purely mechanical responses to information, but are influenced by investors' knowledge, preferences, and perceptions of financial products (Mutawally et al., 2019).

Empirical evidence in Indonesia shows that many individual investors, especially students and young adults, still face difficulties in making informed investment decisions due to their limited understanding of capital market mechanisms and products (Safryani et al., 2020). Research also documents that factors such as investment education, perceived risk and return, and technological facilities provided by financial institutions play an important role in shaping whether and how individuals decide to invest in capital market instruments (Adnyana & Iswanto, 2021). In this study, investment decisions are conceptualized as the extent to which investors decide to allocate their funds to banking sector stocks based on their assessment of the available information, risks, returns, and available technological support.

Financial Literacy on Investment Decisions in Banking Sector Stocks

Financial literacy is an individual's ability to understand basic financial concepts, interpret economic information, and apply this knowledge to make sound financial decisions (Wang et al., 2024). In the context of investing, this includes knowledge of risk-return trade-offs, diversification, and the characteristics of instruments such as stocks and mutual funds (Gustika & Yaspita, 2021). Financial literacy equips individuals with the knowledge and skills needed to interpret financial information, compare alternative instruments, and assess risk-return trade-offs, thereby supporting more structured and rational investment decisions (Gustika & Yaspita, 2021). Previous studies have shown that higher financial literacy is linked to greater participation in capital markets and a higher likelihood of deciding to invest in stocks, especially among students and young investors (Khairiyati & Krisnawati, 2019; Nurchayati & Perkasa, 2024; Siregar & Anggraeni, 2022). Within the Theory of Planned Behavior framework, financial literacy can be seen as a behavioral belief shaping positive attitudes toward investing when individuals believe that their financial knowledge will help them achieve the desired investment outcomes. Based on the explanation above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H1: Financial literacy has a positive effect on investment decisions in banking sector stocks.

Risk Perception on Investment Decisions in Banking Sector Stocks

Risk perception refers to the process of how investor view, assess, and interpret the risks of an investment instrument related to investment decisions (Putri & Ishanah, 2020). Before investing in stocks, investors naturally engage in risk mitigation. This aims to prevent risks such as stock price declines and liquidation. Risk perception is also understood as a factor influencing investment decision-making, as investors who can properly utilize their risk perceptions tend to be more cautious and measured in their investments (Badriatin et al., 2022). According to Nadia & Ritonga, (2022), risk perception can be measured through several indicators: performance risk, financial risk, physical risk, social risk, psychological risk, and time risk. In the context of banking sector stocks, risk perception reflects the extent to which investors assess the potential losses and uncertainties they may face when investing in bank stocks.

Using the theory of planned behavior, risk perception is identified as control beliefs. If individuals believe that the risks they will face are low, they believe the potential benefits will be high, and vice versa. Previous research has shown that higher perceived risk tends to reduce individuals' willingness to allocate funds to risky assets, as investors become more cautious and may avoid stock investments when they perceive the likelihood of losses to be high (Listyani et al., 2021; Mardikaningsih, 2019). The relationship between Risk Perception and Investment Decisions can be explained in the following hypothesis:

H2: Risk perception has a negative effect on investment decisions in banking sector stocks.

Return Perception on Investment Decision in Banking Sector Stocks

Return perception refers to investor expectations of the potential profits from investments, including capital gains and regular income such as dividends (Khairul, 2020). When investors believe that an asset offers attractive expected returns, they tend to show a stronger interest and greater willingness to allocate funds to that asset (Widiantika et al., 2021). As investors, considering the expected rate of return is natural when investing in stocks, especially in the banking sector. Prior research shows that more favorable return expectations increase interest and decisions to invest in financial products such as stocks and mutual funds, particularly among novice investors seeking higher returns than those offered by traditional savings instruments (Junaidi, 2019; Prasetio et al., 2023; Salsabila & Wahyullah, 2022).

From the Theory of Planned Behavior perspective, return perception is categorized as behavioral beliefs because it relates to an individual's belief in the benefits or positive outcomes that will be gained by engaging in investment behavior. However, the degree to which return perception influences investment decisions may vary, depending on how investors balance expected returns with perceived risks. The higher the return received, the greater the investors' interest in stock investment; conversely, when the potential return is minimal, investors become less interested in stock investments (Kusnandar et al., 2022). The hypothesis drawn from the

preceding paragraph is as follows:

H3: Return perception has a positive effect on investment decisions in banking sector stocks.

Technological Advancement on Investment Decision in Banking Sector Stocks.

Technological advancement refers to the stage where the era has evolved with many technological changes, making it easier to obtain information (Nurfadilah et al., 2022). Technological advancement simplifies activities and increases the effectiveness of various aspects of life, including the financial sector through financial technology (Ainiyah & Indrarini, 2022). Financial technology enables transactions and investment information access to be conducted faster, more easily, and efficiently through digital applications and platforms. With technological advancement, investors naturally find it easier to invest, for example, through easily accessible investment apps and other online investment platforms. Technological progress in financial services such as online trading platforms, mobile apps, and digital information systems can reduce entry barriers and facilitate access to the capital market (Mauliddia & Wibowo, 2025). According to Yusuf, (2019), technological advancement is seen from three indicators: perception of usefulness, perception of ease, and perception of convenience in using technology for investing. Various previous studies show that user-friendly digital investment facilities and financial technology services are positively associated with interest in and decisions to invest in stocks (Adnyana & Iswanto, 2021; Fadila et al., 2022; Nurfadilah et al., 2022; Umayka & H.S, 2024).

Within the TPB framework, technological advancement can be seen as a component of control beliefs because it increases investors' sense of ease and ability to manage the investment process in banking sector stocks. Investors have greater confidence in using technology for investments. They also feel that technology significantly helps them understand the market, manage portfolios, and reduce risks, which ultimately affects investment decisions. The following hypothesis can be formulated regarding the relationship between Technological Advancement and Investment Decisions:

H4: Technological advancement has a positive effect on investment decisions in banking sector stocks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Population and Sample

The population in this study consists of all individuals who have invested in stocks and are in the early productive age range, namely 17–34 years old, residing in Central Java Province. The selection of this age range is based on the consideration that this group is in the early stages of financial planning and is beginning to actively utilize investment instruments as part of personal financial management. In addition, technological developments and the digitization of financial services have made this age group relatively more familiar with the use of online investment applications and platforms, making them relevant to the variables to be tested. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, which is a non-probability sampling technique where samples are selected based on certain criteria set by the researcher. The criteria for respondents in this study included:

- (1) having invested in stock instruments,
- (2) being between 17 and 34 years old, and
- (3) residing in the Central Java region.

The sample size was determined using the Slovin formula based on the population of people aged 17–34 years in Central Java according to data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), with a margin of error of 10%. The calculation resulted in a minimum sample requirement of approximately 100 respondents, and to increase the reliability of the results, the researcher set the target sample size slightly above the minimum number. Data collection yielded 139 questionnaires, but after screening based on eligibility criteria, 9 questionnaires were deemed ineligible because the respondents did not have experience investing in banking sector stocks. Thus, the total number of questionnaires used in the analysis was 130 respondents, or approximately 93.5% of the returned questionnaires. This number met the minimum sample size requirement according to Slovin's calculation and was deemed adequate for performing multiple linear regression analysis in accordance with the research objectives.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Normality Test

Normality testing is an important part of classical assumption diagnostics in this study because it is used to assess whether the analyzed data is normally distributed. Normality testing was performed using Kolmogorov–Smirnov at a significance level of 5% (0.05), considering that a large sample size (130 respondents) is appropriate for this procedure in detecting deviations from normal distribution. The results of the normality test presented in the table form the empirical basis for assessing the adequacy of the data and ensuring the feasibility of using multiple linear regression analysis in the next stage.

Table 1: Normality Test Result

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test	
	Unstandardized Residual
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.200

Source: Author's processing with SPSS version 24, 2024

As shown in the normality test results table, a significance value of 0.200 was obtained. Since this value is greater than the significance level of 0.05, the data in this study can be said to be normally distributed. Thus, the assumption of normality in the regression model has been met, so the data is considered suitable for further analysis using multiple linear regression.

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity testing is conducted to assess whether there is a strong relationship or correlation between independent variables in a multiple linear regression model. Multicollinearity detection is performed by examining the tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for each independent variable. The model is declared free of multicollinearity issues if the tolerance value is greater than 0.10 and the VIF value is less than 10.

Table 2: Multicollinearity Test Result

<u>Collinearity</u>		
Statistics		
Model	<i>Tolerance</i>	VIF
Financial Literacy	0.497	2.013
Risk Perception	0.442	2.260
Return Perception	0.452	2.212
Technological Advancement	0.768	1.302
Dependent Variable: Keputusan Investasi		

Source: Author’s processing with SPSS version 24, 2024

Based on the results presented in the table, all independent variables have tolerance values above 0.10 and VIF values below 10. Thus, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity in this study, so that the multiple regression model used has met the multicollinearity assumption.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is used to see whether there is inequality in the residual variance from one observation to another in the regression model. In this study, the test was conducted using the Glejser method, which involves regressing the absolute residual values against the independent variables and then evaluating the resulting significance values (Sig.). The regression model is declared free of heteroscedasticity if the significance values of all independent variables are greater than 0.05.

Table 3: Heteroscedasticity Test Result

Model	t	Sig.
(Constant)	0.813	0.418
Financial Literacy	0.047	0.963
Risk Perception	-1.333	0.185
Return Perception	0.650	0.517
Technological Advancement	0.845	0.400

Source: Author’s processing with SPSS version 24, 2024

Based on the estimation results presented in the table, the significance value of each independent variable is above 0.05. This indicates that there is no heteroscedasticity in this study, so the assumption of homoscedasticity is considered fulfilled and the error variance can be assumed to be constant across all observations.

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Multiple linear regression analysis was used to determine the direction and magnitude of the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable, namely investment decisions. The estimation results are summarized in Table 4, which presents the regression coefficients, t-values, and statistical significance for each variable.

Table 4: Multiple Linear Regression Test Result

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized		
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	β	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	7.147	2.265		3.155	0.002
FinancialLiteracy	0.203	0.054	0.345	3.736	0.001
RiskPerception	0.049	0.072	0.066	0.677	0.499
ReturnPerception	0.191	0.137	0.135	1.393	0.166
TechnologicalAdvancement	0.406	0.101	0.299	4.030	0.001

a. Dependent Variable: Investment Decision

Source: Author’s processing with SPSS version 24, 2024

Based on Table 4, the multiple linear regression equation using unstandardized coefficients (β) can be written as follows:

$$Y = 7.147 + 0.203X_1 + 0.049X_2 + 0.191X_3 + 0.406X_4$$

where Y is investment decision, X_1 financial literacy, X_2 risk perception, X_3 return perception, and X_4 technological advancement. The constant value of 7.147 indicates that when all independent variables are zero, the investment decision value is estimated to be 7.147. The financial literacy coefficient of 0.203 means that, assuming other variables remain constant, a one-unit increase in financial literacy will increase the investment decision score by 0.203. The risk perception coefficient of 0.049 indicates that each one-unit increase in risk perception, ceteris paribus, will increase the investment decision by 0.049. The return perception coefficient of 0.191 shows that a one-unit increase in return perception, with other variables remaining constant, will increase investment decisions by 0.191. Meanwhile, the technological progress coefficient of 0.406 implies that every one-unit increase in technological progress will be followed by an increase in investment decisions of 0.406, assuming other variables remain constant.

Determinant Test (R²)

The coefficient of determination test is used to assess how much of the variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables in a multiple linear regression model. In this study, this information is viewed through the R Square value and especially the Adjusted R Square reported in the regression output, because this adjusted value is more appropriate to use when the model involves several independent variables.

Table 5: Determinant Test Result

R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R
0.685	0.470	0.453	2.201

Source: Author’s processing with SPSS version 24, 2024

Based on Table 5, the Adjusted R Square value obtained is 0.453. This indicates that approximately 45.3% of the variation in investment decisions can be explained simultaneously by the variables of financial literacy, risk perception, return perception, and technological advancement, while the remaining 54.7% is influenced by other factors outside the model that were not examined in this study.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Financial Literacy on Investment Decisions in Banking Stocks

Based on the regression test results in Table 4, the financial literacy variable (X_1) has a significance value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that financial literacy has a significant effect on investment decisions (Y) in the banking sector. This finding shows that the higher an individual's level of financial literacy, the greater their tendency to make more planned and rational investment decisions. Financial literacy in this case includes an understanding of basic financial concepts, the ability to manage personal finances, and an understanding of the risks and potential returns of investment instruments (Safriyani et al., 2020). The results of the study indicate that the majority of respondents have a relatively good level of financial literacy, so they are more careful in managing their assets and tend to make careful considerations before investing in banking stocks. This finding is consistent with previous studies which state that high financial literacy correlates with more structured investment behavior and a greater tendency to engage in investment activities (Gustika & Yaspita, 2021; Khairiyati & Krisnawati, 2019; Nurchayati & Perkasa, 2024; Siregar & Anggraeni, 2022). Thus, the results of this study support the first hypothesis (H1) that financial literacy has a significant

effect on investment decisions in the banking sector.

Effect of Risk Perception on Investment Decision in Banking Stocks

Based on the regression test results in Table 4, the risk perception variable (X2) has a significance value of 0.499, which is greater than the significance threshold of 0.05. This indicates that risk perception does not have a significant effect on investment decisions (Y) in banking sector stocks, even though the regression coefficient is positive. In other words, differences in the level of risk perception among respondents are not statistically proven to influence their decision to invest in banking stocks.

In this study, risk perception was measured through six indicators, namely performance risk, financial risk, physical risk, social risk, psychological risk, and time risk. The results of the analysis show that the perception of these various types of risk is not strong enough to be the main determinant in respondents' investment decisions in banking sector stocks. One possible explanation is that respondents have relatively good financial literacy, so they view risk as a normal and inherent part of investment activities and try to manage it through various strategies, so that concerns about potential losses do not dominate their decisions (Adnyana & Iswanto, 2021).

These findings are in line with several previous studies that show that risk perception does not always have a significant effect on investment decisions, especially when investors feel capable of understanding and controlling risk, or when their decisions are driven more by other factors such as market trends, social influence, or intuitive judgment (Mutawally et al., 2019; Prasetyo et al., 2023; Putri & Ishanah, 2020). Thus, the results of this study do not support the second hypothesis (H2), which states that risk perception influence investment decisions in the banking sector.

Effect of Return Perception on Investment Decision in Banking Stocks

Based on the estimation results in Table 4, the return perception variable has a significance value of 0.166, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This indicates that return perception does not have a significant effect on investment decisions in banking sector stocks in this study. Thus, differences in the level of return perception among respondents have not been statistically proven to be a major determinant in their decision to invest in banking stocks.

In this study, return perception is measured through three main indicators, namely expectations of dividends, capital gains, and bonus shares as forms of potential profit from stock ownership. The results of the analysis show that expectations of these three forms of return have not been a dominant consideration in respondents' investment decisions. One possible explanation is that the benefits of these three indicators are generally realized over a longer period of time and are perceived to be associated with higher risks, so investors tend to prioritize other aspects such as price stability, company fundamentals, and long-term prospects (Savanah & Takarini, 2021).

These findings are in line with several previous studies that show that perceived returns do not always have a significant effect on investment decisions, especially in dynamic and uncertain market conditions, where investors focus more on the security and stability of investments or do not fully understand return mechanisms such as dividends and capital gain (Adnyana & Iswanto, 2021; Khairul, 2020; Widiatika et al., 2021). Thus, the results of this study do not support the third hypothesis (H3), which states that perceived returns influence investment decisions in the banking sector.

Effect of Technological Advancement on Investment Decision in Banking Stocks.

Based on the estimation results in Table 4, the technological advancement variable has a significance value of 0.001, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. This value indicates that technological advancement has a significant effect on investment decisions in the banking sector stocks. A positive regression coefficient indicates that the higher the level of technological advancement perceived by investors, the higher their tendency to make investment decisions.

In this study, technological advancement is measured through perceptions of usefulness, ease of use, and comfort in using technology for investment activities. The results of the study indicate that the majority of respondents view technology as a means of simplifying the transaction process, facilitating the monitoring of stock price movements, and providing relevant and easily accessible information, thereby increasing confidence in making investment decisions in banking sector stocks (Nurfadilah et al., 2022)

These findings are consistent with previous studies that state that technological advances play an important role in facilitating access to capital markets, encouraging more proactive investment behavior, and enabling faster and more independent decision-making through digital platforms (Umayka & Sufyati, 2024; Yusuf, 2019). Thus, technological advances can be considered a significant determining factor in investment decisions in the banking sector, and the fourth hypothesis (H4) in this study is accepted.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion, several conclusions were drawn as follows. (1) Financial literacy has a positive and significant effect on investment decisions in the banking sector, indicating that the higher an individual's level of financial knowledge and understanding, the greater their tendency to make more planned investment decisions in banking stocks. (2) Risk perception does not have a significant effect on investment decisions, so that the level of risk perceived by investors is not yet a determining factor in their decision to invest in banking stocks. (3) Return perception also does not have a significant effect on investment decisions, indicating that expectations of dividends, capital gains, and bonus shares are not yet a major consideration in

respondents' investment decisions. (4) Technological advances have a positive and significant effect on investment decisions, meaning that the existence and use of digital investment technology that is considered useful, easy, and convenient encourages individuals to invest in banking sector stocks.

IMPLICATION

The implications of this study are as follows: (1) The significant effect of financial literacy on investment decisions implies that strengthening financial education programs can play an important role in improving the quality of investors' decision-making in banking stocks. (2) The insignificant effect of risk perception and return perception shows that investors rely more on other considerations such as issuer fundamentals and price stability. Therefore, efforts are needed to improve the way information related to risk and return is communicated so that it is better understood and properly used in decision making. (3) The finding that technological advances have a significant effect on investment decisions underscores the importance of developing and strengthening secure, accessible, and user-friendly digital investment platform infrastructure to encourage broader and higher-quality participation in the banking sector stock market.

SUGGESTIONS

The recommendations obtained from this study are as follows: (1) Policymakers, financial institutions, and educational institutions are advised to intensify financial literacy programs, especially those focused on practical investment skills, to improve the quality of investment decisions in the banking sector. (2) For future researchers, it is recommended to add other behavioral and psychological variables such as overconfidence, herding, or investment motivation, and to consider different sectors or asset classes, so that other factors affecting investment decisions beyond risk and return perceptions can be described more comprehensively. (3) Practitioners and regulators should continue to develop and refine secure, user-friendly, and widely accessible digital investment platforms to leverage technological advances as a catalyst for broader and more informed participation in the capital market.

REFERENCES

- Adnyana, I. M., & Iswanto, H. (2021). The Influence of Investment Education, Risk Perception, and Technological Advances on Students' Interest in Stock Investment. *Open Access Indonesia Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(1), 132–142. <https://journalsocialsciences.com/index.php/OAIJSS>
- Ainiyah, N., & Indrarini, R. (2022). Pengaruh Motivasi Investasi dan Kemajuan Teknologi terhadap Minat Berinvestasi di Reksadana Syariah pada Generasi Z Kota Surabaya. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islami*, 5(22), 80–94. <https://journal.unesa.ac.id/index.php/jeif>
- Ajzen, I. (1991). *The Theory of Planned Behavior*.
- Amaliyah, F., & Herwiyanti, E. (2020). Pengaruh Keputusan Investasi, Ukuran Perusahaan, Keputusan Pendanaan dan Kebijakan Deviden Terhadap Nilai Perusahaan Sektor Pertambangan. *Jurnal Penelitian Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 5(1), 39–51. <https://doi.org/10.33633/jpeb.v5i1.2783>
- Arning, K., Linzenich, A., Ziefle, M., Meuleneers, L., Rezo, D., & Aßen, N. Von Der. (2024). Eliciting laypeople's mental models and risk perceptions of direct air carbon capture and storage: Implications for effective risk communication. *Energy Reports*, 12(May), 1068–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2024.06.070>
- Badriatin, T., Rinandiyana, L. R., & Marino, W. S. (2022). Persepsi Risiko Dan Sikap Toleransi Risiko Terhadap Keputusan Investasi Mahasiswa. *Jurnal Perspektif*, 20(2), 158–163. <https://doi.org/10.31294/jp.v20i2.13596>
- Fadila, N., Goso, G., Hamid, R. S., & Ukkas, I. (2022). Pengaruh Literasi Keuangan, Financial Technology, Persepsi Risiko, dan Locus of Control Terhadap Keputusan Investasi Pengusaha Muda. *Owner*, 6(2), 1633–1643. <https://doi.org/10.33395/owner.v6i2.789>
- Gustika, G. S., & Yaspita, H. (2021). Pengaruh Literasi Keuangan Terhadap Keputusan Investasi Mahasiswa STIE Indragiri Rengat. *J-MAS (Jurnal Manajemen Dan Sains)*, 6(1), 261. <https://doi.org/10.33087/jmas.v6i1.252>
- Junaidi, E. T. N. D. (2019). Pengaruh Norma Subjektif, Motivasi Investasi, Pengetahuan Investasi, Persepsi Return Dan Literasi Keuangan Terhadap Minat Mahasiswa Berinvestasi Saham Di Pasar Modal ((Studi Empiris Pada Mahasiswa Akuntansi FEB UNISMA dan UNIBRAW di Malang). *E-Jra*, 08(05), 9–19.
- Khairiyati, C., & Krisnawati, A. (2019). Analisis Pengaruh Literasi Keuangan Terhadap Keputusan Investasi Pada Masyarakat Kota Bandung. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 3(2), 301–312.
- Khairul, M. (2020). pengaruh pengetahuan investasi , persepsi return , dan motivasi investasi syariah bursa efek indonesia IAIN Batusangkar. *Jurnal Ilmiah Indonesia*, 5(6), 120–128.
- Kling, L., König-Kersting, C., & Trautmann, S. T. (2023). Investment preferences and risk perception: Financial agents versus clients. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2022.106489>
- KSEI Indonesia Central Securities Depository. (2024). Statistik Pasar Modal Indonesia. *Publikasi PT Kustodian Sentral Efek Indonesia*, September, 1–7. https://www.ksei.co.id/publications/demografi_investor

14. Kusnandar, D. L., Sari, D. P., & Sahroni, N. (2022). Pengaruh Literasi Digital dan Persepsi Return dan Risiko dalam Meningkatkan Minat Investasi Generasi Z di Pasar Modal pada Era New Normal. *Valid Jurnal Ilmiah*, 20(1), 97–104.
15. Li, W. Y., & Paudel, T. (2024). Risk perception, policy efficacy, and policy support in earthquake risk management: Empirical insights from South Korea. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 23(May), 100349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pdisas.2024.100349>
16. Listyani, T. T., Rois, M., & Prihati, S. (2021). Analisis Pengaruh Pengetahuan Investasi, Pelatihan Pasar Modal, Modal Investasi Minimal Dan Persepsi Risiko Terhadap Minat Investasi Mahasiswa Di Pasar Modal (Studi pada PT. Phintraco Sekuritas Branch Office Semarang). *Die Satzung Des Völkerbundes*, 2(1), 255–257. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783112372760-032>
17. Mardikaningsih, R. (2019). Pengaruh Persepsi Kualitas Dan Persepsi Resiko Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Susu Formula. *Ekuitas*, 1(1), 1–8. <http://repository.uhn.ac.id/handle/123456789/3115%0Ahttp://repository.uhn.ac.id/bitstream/handle/123456789/3115/MegaRumintangPanjaitan.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
18. Mauliddia, S. A., & Wibowo, P. A. (2025). PENGARUH LITERASI KEUANGAN, PENDAPATAN, Efikasi Keuangan TERHADAP KEPUTUSAN INVESTASI DENGAN TEKNOLOGI DIGITAL SEBAGAI VARIABEL MODERASI. *Nobel Management Review*, 6(2), 358–372.
19. Mutawally, F. W., Haryono, N. A., & Cahyani, O. S. (2019). Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhi Keputusan Investasi di Pasar Modal Indonesia (Studi Empiris pada Mahasiswa yang Bertempat Tinggal di Kota Magelang). *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen (JIM)*, 7(4), 942–953.
20. Nadia, & Ritonga, N. (2022). PENGARUH PERCEIVED OF RISK (PERSEPSI RISIKO) TERHADAP MINAT BELI ONLINE (Studi Pada Masyarakat Dusun 1 Desa Tambon Tunong Kecamatan Dewantara Kabupaten Aceh Utara). *Repository.Ummat.Ac.Id*, 5(April), 39–53. [https://repository.ummat.ac.id/879/1/BAB I SAMPE 3.pdf](https://repository.ummat.ac.id/879/1/BAB%20I%20SAMPE%203.pdf)
21. Nurchayati, S., & Perkasa, D. H. (2024). Peran Illusion of Control, Literasi Keuangan Dan Bias Overconfidence Dalam Mempengaruhi Keputusan Investasi Dipasar Modal *Jurnal Bina Bangsa*17(2). <https://www.jbbe.lppmbinabangsa.id/index.php/jbbe/article/view/544%0Ahttps://www.jbbe.lppmbinabangsa.id/index.php/jbbe/article/download/544/311>
22. Nurfadilah, N., Wahyuni, I., & Subaida, I. (2022). Pengaruh Pengetahuan Investasi Dan Kemajuan Teknologi Terhadap Keputusan Investasi Dengan Minat Investasi Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi Mahasiswa Prodi Manajemen Universitas Abdurachman Saleh Situbondo). *Jurnal Mahasiswa Entrepreneurship (JME)*, 1(8), 1630. <https://doi.org/10.36841/jme.v1i8.2209>
23. Otoritas Jasa Keuangan. (2024a). *Capital Market Weekly Statistics* (Issue November).
24. Otoritas Jasa Keuangan. (2024b). *Edukasi Keuangan*. Otoritas Jasa Keuangan. <https://klc.kemenkeu.go.id/tata-cara-pemusnahan-bmn-di-kuasa-pengguna-barang/>
25. Pramono, B. S. H. Y. (2023). *Pengaruh pengetahuan investasi syariah, ekspektasi return dan pemahaman kemajuan teknologi terhadap minat investasi mahasiswa di pasar modal*. 4(3), 413–425.
26. Prasetyo, R., Iswanaji, C., & Khotijah, S. A. (2023). Pengaruh Persepsi Return, Risiko, Pengetahuan dan Religiusitas Terhadap Minat Berinvestasi di Pasar Modal Syariah. *Al-Intaj : Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 9(1), 88. <https://doi.org/10.29300/aij.v9i1.9651>
27. Pratama, A., Fauzi, A., & Purwohedi, U. (2022). Pengaruh Persepsi Risiko, Ekspektasi Return, dan Behavioral Motivation Terhadap Keputusan Investasi Mahasiswa yang Terdaftar di Galeri Investasi pada Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Jakarta. *Indonesian Journal of Economy, Business, Entrepreneurship and Finance*, 2(3), 252–267. <https://doi.org/10.53067/ijebef.v2i3>
28. Putri, R. A., & Ishanah, Y. (2020). Faktor-Faktor Yang Memengaruhi Keputusan Investasi PadaInvestor Saham Di Surabaya. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 8(1), 197–209.
29. Safryani, U., Aziz, A., & Triwahyuningtyas, N. (2020). Analisis Literasi Keuangan, Perilaku Keuangan, Dan Pendapatan Terhadap Keputusan Investasi. *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi Kesatuan*, 8(3), 319–332. <https://doi.org/10.37641/jiakes.v8i3.384>
30. Salsabila, F., & Wahyullah, M. (2022). Analisis Pengaruh Pelatihan, Pengetahuan, Dan Persepsi Return Terhadap Keputusan Berinvestasi Reksadana (Studi Kasus pada Mahasiswa STIE AMM Mataram Tahun 2021). *Journal Ilmiah Rinjani : Media Informasi Ilmiah Universitas Gunung Rinjani*, 10(2), 83–90. <https://doi.org/10.53952/jir.v10i2.426>
31. Savanah, A. N., & Takarini, N. (2021). Analisis Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Minat Investasi Keuangan Pada Mahasiswa Manajemen Upn “Veteran” Jawa Timur. *Jurnal Sosial Ekonomi Dan Politik*, 2, 84–92.
32. Siregar, D. K., & Anggraeni, D. R. (2022). *Pengaruh Literasi Keuangan Dan Perilaku Keuangan Terhadap Keputusan Investasi Mahasiswa*. 2(1), 96–112.
33. Subowo, T. (2022). Pengaruh Literasi keuangan, kemajuan teknologi, persepsi return dan risiko terhadap minat berinvestasi di pasar modal. *Fortunate Business Review*, 2(1), 20–31. https://scholar.google.co.id/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&as_vis=1&q=Determinan+yang+Berpengaruh+pada+Minat+

Investasi+di+Pasar+Modal&btnG=

34. Umayka, S., & H.S, S. (2024). Faktor-Faktor Yang Memengaruhi Keputusan Pembelian Produk Halal Umkm Di Dki Jakarta. *Ekono Insentif*, 18(1), 24–33. <https://doi.org/10.36787/jei.v18i1.1350>
35. Usman, B., Hasnam, M. G., Nurazi, R., Baihaqi, & Aujirapongpan, S. (2024). Exploring investor attention in Shariah markets, macroeconomic influences, and corporate performance: Insights from Indonesia. *Social Sciences and Humanities Open*, 10(June), 101015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2024.101015>
36. Wang, G., Zhang, M., & He, B. (2024). Financial literacy and investment returns: The moderating effect of education level. *Finance Research Letters*, 67(PA), 105781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2024.105781>
37. Widiatika, M., Mardiyati, U., & Ahmad, G. N. (2021). The Effect of Return Perception, Motivation, Financial Literacy, and Income on Investment Interest of Students at State University of Jakarta. *Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 5(1), 86–112. <https://doi.org/10.21009/jdmb.05.1.5>
38. Yusuf, M. (2019). Pengaruh Kemajuan Teknologi dan Pengetahuan terhadap Minat Generasi Milenial dalam Berinvestasi di Pasar Modal. *Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 2(2), 86–94. <https://doi.org/10.21009/jdmb.02.2.3>